

**ON THE x -COORDINATES OF PELL EQUATIONS WHICH ARE
NARAYANA NUMBERS**

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Abstract

The sequence of Narayana numbers $\{N_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is recursively given by $N_{n+3} = N_{n+2} + N_n$ with the initial conditions $N_0 = 0, N_1 = N_2 = 1$. In this work it is shown that there exists at most one value of $x > 0$ satisfying the Pell equation $x^2 - dy^2 = \pm 1$, which is a Narayana number except for $d = 2$. Baker's theory of nonzero linear forms in logarithms of algebraic numbers, the Baker-Davenport reduction procedure, as well as the elementary properties of Narayana's sequence, are used to prove the main result. All computations are done with the help of a computer program in *Mathematica*.

1. Introduction

Consider the Pell equation

$$x^2 - dy^2 = \pm 1 \tag{1}$$

with a square free integer $d > 1$. All the positive integer solutions (x, y) of Equation (1) are given by

$$x_n + y_n \sqrt{d} = (x_1 + y_1 \sqrt{d})^n$$

for some $n \geq 1$, with the fundamental solution (x_1, y_1) . The sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ forms a binary recurrent sequence and the formula

$$x_n = \frac{(x_1 + y_1 \sqrt{d})^n + (x_1 - y_1 \sqrt{d})^n}{2}$$

holds for all $n \geq 1$.

Many authors studied various Diophantine equations involving members of the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ or $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ which belong to some interesting sequences such as

Fibonacci sequence, Lucas sequence, Tribonacci sequence, Padovan sequence, etc. For instance, Luca and Togbé [20] considered the Diophantine equation

$$x_n = F_m, \tag{2}$$

where x_n are the x -coordinates of the solutions of Equation (1) and $\{F_m\}_{m \geq 0}$ denotes the sequence of Fibonacci numbers. The authors proved that Equation (2) has at most one solution n for all d except $d = 2$, in which it has two solutions. Kafle et al. [16] solved the Diophantine equation

$$x_n = L_m,$$

where $\{L_m\}_{m \geq 0}$ is the sequence of Lucas numbers and proved that it has at most one solution (n, m) except the case $d = 2$, in which case it has four solutions, namely, $(1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 2), (3, 4)$. In [19], Luca et al. studied a similar problem but with the sequence of Tribonacci numbers given by $T_{m+3} = T_{m+2} + T_{m+1} + T_m$, with $T_0 = 0, T_1 = T_2 = 1$. They showed that the equation

$$x_n = T_m$$

has at most one solution (n, m) except when $d = 2$ and $d = 3$, in which cases it has solutions $(n, m) = (1, 1), (1, 2), (3, 5)$ and $(n, m) = (1, 3), (2, 5)$, respectively. Later, Bravo et al.[3] proved that for each square free integer d , there is at most one positive integer k such that x_k admits a representation as

$$x_k = T_m + T_n$$

for some nonnegative integers $0 \leq m \leq n$, except for $d \in \{2, 3, 5, 15, 26\}$. In [7], Ddamulira found all the solutions to the x -coordinates of Pell equations that are sums of two Padovan numbers. Several researchers have looked into related problems involving the intersection of the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ with linear recurrence sequences (see [4], [6], [8], [10], [11], [12], [14], [15], [17],[22]).

For most of the sequences it is expected that, the solution to the x - coordinate of Pell Equation (1) has at most one positive integer solution for any value of d except for finitely many. In this study, we consider the sequence of Narayana numbers and show that the solution to the x -coordinate of Pell Equation (1) has at most one positive integer solution for any value d except for $d = 2$.

Narayana numbers originated from a herd of cows and calves problem which was proposed by the Indian mathematician Narayana Pandit [1]. Narayana’s cows sequence $\{N_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is recursively defined as

$$N_{n+3} = N_{n+2} + N_n,$$

for $n \geq 0$ with initial condition $(N_0, N_1, N_2) = (0, 1, 1)$. It is the sequence [A000930](#) in the OEIS (Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences). The first few terms are

$$0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9, 13, 19, 28, 41, \dots$$

The characteristic polynomial of this sequence is given by $f(x) = x^3 - x^2 - 1$ which has zeros α (≈ 1.46557) and two conjugate complex zeros β and γ with $|\beta| = |\gamma| < 1$. Narayana's cows sequence has Binet's formula

$$N_n = a\alpha^n + b\beta^n + c\gamma^n \text{ for all } n \geq 0,$$

with

$$a = \frac{\alpha}{(\alpha - \beta)(\alpha - \gamma)}, \quad b = \frac{\beta}{(\beta - \alpha)(\beta - \gamma)}, \quad c = \frac{\gamma}{(\gamma - \alpha)(\gamma - \beta)}.$$

This can also be rewritten as $N_n = C_\alpha\alpha^{n+2} + C_\beta\beta^{n+2} + C_\gamma\gamma^{n+2}$ for all $n \geq 0$ where $C_x = \frac{1}{x^3+2}$ for $x \in \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$. The minimal polynomial of C_α is $31x^3 - 31x^2 + 10x - 1$ and all of its zeros lie inside the unit circle. One can estimate the following for α, C_α and $C_\beta\beta^{n+2} + C_\gamma\gamma^{n+2}$:

$$1.46 < \alpha < 1.47; \quad 5.14 < C_\alpha^{-1} < 5.15; \quad |C_\beta\beta^{n+2} + C_\gamma\gamma^{n+2}| < 1/2 \text{ for all } n \geq 1.$$

By induction it is easy to prove that

$$\alpha^{n-2} \leq N_n \leq \alpha^{n-1} \text{ for all } n \geq 1. \tag{3}$$

Our main theorem will be the following.

Theorem 1. *Let $d \geq 2$ be a square free integer. Then the Diophantine equation*

$$x_n = N_m \tag{4}$$

has at most one positive integer solution n for any value of d except for $d = 2$.

2. Preliminaries

Baker's theory plays an important role in reducing the bounds concerning linear forms in logarithms of algebraic numbers. Let η be an algebraic number with minimal primitive polynomial

$$f(X) = a_0x^d + a_1x^{d-1} + \dots + a_d = a_0 \prod_{i=1}^d (X - \eta^{(i)}) \in \mathbb{Z}[X],$$

where the leading coefficient $a_0 > 0$, and $\eta^{(i)}$'s are conjugates of η . Then the logarithmic height of η is given by

$$h(\eta) = \frac{1}{d} \left(\log a_0 + \sum_{j=1}^d \max\{0, \log |\eta^{(j)}|\} \right).$$

The following are some properties of the logarithmic height function (see [23, Property 3.3]) which will be used to calculate the heights of the algebraic integers:

$$\begin{aligned} h(\eta + \gamma) &\leq h(\eta) + h(\gamma) + \log 2, \\ h(\eta\gamma^{\pm 1}) &\leq h(\eta) + h(\gamma), \\ h(\eta^k) &= |k|h(\eta), k \in \mathbb{Z}. \end{aligned}$$

With these notation, Matveev (see [21] or [5, Theorem 9.4]) proved the following result.

Theorem 2. *Let $\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_l$ be positive real algebraic integers in a real algebraic number field \mathbb{L} of degree $d_{\mathbb{L}}$ and b_1, b_2, \dots, b_l be nonzero integers. If $\Gamma = \prod_{i=1}^l \eta_i^{b_i} - 1$ is not zero, then*

$$\log |\Gamma| > -1.4 \cdot 30^{l+3} l^{4.5} d_{\mathbb{L}}^2 (1 + \log d_{\mathbb{L}}) (1 + \log D) A_1 A_2 \dots A_l,$$

where $D = \max\{|b_1|, |b_2|, \dots, |b_l|\}$ and A_1, A_2, \dots, A_l are positive real numbers such that

$$A_j \geq \max\{d_{\mathbb{L}} h(\eta_j), |\log \eta_j|, 0.16\} \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, l.$$

When $l = 2$ and η_1, η_2 are positive and multiplicatively independent, we can use a result of Laurent, Mignotte and Nesterenko [18]. Let B_1, B_2 be real numbers greater than 1 such that

$$\log B_i = \max \left\{ h(\eta_i), \frac{|\log \eta_i|}{d_{\mathbb{L}}}, \frac{1}{d_{\mathbb{L}}} \right\} \text{ for } i = 1, 2$$

and

$$b' = \frac{|b_1|}{d_{\mathbb{L}} \log B_2} + \frac{|b_2|}{d_{\mathbb{L}} \log B_1}.$$

We put

$$\Lambda := b_1 \log \eta_1 + b_2 \log \eta_2.$$

Note that $\Lambda \neq 0$ when η_1 and η_2 are multiplicatively independent. With the above notation, we have the following result.

Theorem 3. *If η_1, η_2 are positive and multiplicatively independent, then*

$$\log |\Lambda| > -24.34 \cdot d_{\mathbb{L}}^4 \left(\max \left\{ \log b' + 0.14, \frac{21}{d_{\mathbb{L}}}, \frac{1}{2} \right\} \right)^2 \log B_1 \log B_2.$$

The following Baker-Davenport reduction method due to Dujella and Pethő [9, Lemma 5] is used to reduce the bounds of the variables that are too large.

Lemma 1. *Let M be a positive integer and p/q be a convergent of the continued fraction of the irrational number τ such that $q > 6M$. Let A, B, μ be real numbers with $A > 0$ and $B > 1$. Let $\varepsilon := \|\mu q\| - M\|\tau q\|$, where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the distance from the nearest integer. If $\varepsilon > 0$, then there exists no solution to the inequality*

$$0 < |u\tau - v + \mu| < AB^{-w}$$

in positive integers u, v, w with

$$u \leq M \text{ and } w \geq \frac{\log(Aq/\varepsilon)}{\log B}.$$

3. Proof of Theorem 1

Let (x_1, y_1) be the fundamental solution of the Pell Equation (1). Putting

$$\delta := x_1 + y_1\sqrt{d} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta := x_1 - y_1\sqrt{d},$$

we get

$$\delta \cdot \eta = x_1^2 - dy_1^2 = \pm 1.$$

Then

$$x_n = \frac{\delta^n + \eta^n}{2}.$$

Since $\delta \geq 1 + \sqrt{2} > \alpha^2$, it follows that

$$\frac{\delta^n}{\alpha^2} < x_n < \frac{\delta^n}{\alpha}. \tag{5}$$

Using inequalities (3) and (5), we get from Equation (4) that

$$\alpha^{m-2} \leq N_m = X_n < \frac{\delta^n}{\alpha}.$$

Taking the logarithm on both sides gives

$$(m - 2) \log \alpha < n \log \delta - \log \alpha,$$

which leads to

$$m \log \alpha < n \log \delta + \log \alpha.$$

Thus,

$$m < n \left(\frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha} \right) + 1.$$

Similarly, $\frac{\delta^n}{\alpha^2} < X_n = N_m \leq \alpha^{m-1}$ gives

$$n \log \delta - 2 \log \alpha < (m - 1) \log \alpha.$$

Thus,

$$n \left(\frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha} \right) - 1 < m.$$

Hence, we obtain

$$n \left(\frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha} \right) - 1 < m < n \left(\frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha} \right) + 1. \tag{6}$$

Using Binet’s formula of Narayana’s cows sequence in Equation (4), we get

$$\frac{1}{2}(\delta^n + \eta^n) = C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2} + C_\beta \beta^{m+2} + C_\gamma \gamma^{m+2}. \tag{7}$$

We can write Equation (7) as

$$\frac{1}{2}\delta^n - C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2} = (C_\beta \beta^{m+2} + C_\gamma \gamma^{m+2}) - \frac{1}{2}\eta^n.$$

Taking absolute values on both sides and dividing by $C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \delta^n (2C_\alpha)^{-1} \alpha^{-(m+2)} - 1 \right| &\leq \left| \frac{1}{2C_\alpha \delta^n \alpha^{m+2}} \right| + \left| \frac{C_\beta \beta^{m+2} + C_\gamma \gamma^{m+2}}{C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2}} \right| \\ &< \frac{1}{2C_\alpha \alpha^{2m+1}} + \frac{1}{2C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2}} \\ &< \frac{1}{2C_\alpha} \frac{2}{\alpha^{m+2}} \\ &< \frac{3}{\alpha^m}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Put

$$\Gamma = \delta^n (2C_\alpha)^{-1} \alpha^{-(m+2)} - 1. \tag{9}$$

We need to show $\Gamma \neq 0$. Suppose $\Gamma = 0$; then

$$\delta^n = 2C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2}.$$

Note that $\delta^n \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{d})$, a quadratic field, while $2C_\alpha \alpha^{m+2} \in \mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$, a cubic field. The intersection of these two fields is \mathbb{Q} . Thus, $\delta^n \in \mathbb{Q}$. Since δ^n is an algebraic integer and $n \geq 1$, it follows that $\delta^n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Since δ is a unit, we get $\delta^n = 1$, so $n = 0$, a contradiction. Therefore, $\Gamma \neq 0$. To apply Theorem 2 in Equation (9), let

$$\eta_1 = \delta, \eta_2 = 2C_\alpha, \eta_3 = \alpha, b_1 = n, b_2 = -1, b_3 = -(m + 2), l = 3,$$

where $\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3 \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{d}, \alpha)$ and $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathbb{Z}$. The degree $d_{\mathbb{L}} = [\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{d}, \alpha) : \mathbb{Q}]$ is 6.

Since $\delta \geq 1 + \sqrt{2} > \alpha^2$, we have $n < m + 2$. Therefore, $D = \max\{1, n, m + 2\} = m + 2$. To estimate the parameters A_1, A_2, A_3 , we calculate the logarithmic heights of η_1, η_2, η_3 as follows

$$h(\eta_1) = \frac{\log \delta}{2}, \quad h(\eta_2) = h(2C_\alpha) \leq h(2) + h(C_\alpha) < 1.84, \quad h(\eta_3) = \frac{\log \alpha}{3} < 0.13.$$

Thus, we can take

$$A_1 = 3 \log \delta, \quad A_2 = 11.04, \quad A_3 = 0.78.$$

By virtue of Theorem 2, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \log |\Gamma| &> -1.4 \cdot 30^6 3^{4.5} 3^2 (1 + \log 6)(1 + \log(m + 2))(3 \log \delta)(11.04)(0.78) \\ &> -9.2 \cdot 10^{13} \log \delta (1 + \log(m + 2)). \end{aligned}$$

Comparing the above inequality with (8) gives

$$m \log \alpha - \log 3 < 9.2 \cdot 10^{13} (\log \delta)(1 + \log(m + 2)).$$

Then we get

$$m \log \alpha < 9.3 \cdot 10^{13} (\log \delta)(1 + \log(m + 2)),$$

and further

$$m < 24.33 \cdot 10^{13} (\log \delta)(1 + \log(m + 2)). \tag{10}$$

Using (6) we get

$$n \log \delta < m \log \alpha + \log \alpha,$$

which implies

$$n < 9.4 \cdot 10^{13} (1 + \log(m + 2)). \tag{11}$$

Now, we summarize what we have proved so far.

Lemma 2. *All solutions to Equation (4) satisfy*

$$m < 24.33 \cdot 10^{13} (\log \delta)(1 + \log(m + 2)) \quad \text{and} \quad n < 9.4 \cdot 10^{13} (1 + \log(m + 2)).$$

Now, define a linear form in two logarithms

$$\Lambda := n \log \delta - \log(2C_\alpha) - (m + 2) \log \alpha.$$

Since $|e^\Lambda - 1| < 1/2$ for $m \geq 5$, it follows that

$$|\Lambda| < 2|e^\Lambda - 1| < \frac{6}{\alpha^m}.$$

Let (n_1, m_1) and (n_2, m_2) be two pairs of positive integers such that

$$x_{n_1} = N_{m_1} \text{ and } x_{n_2} = N_{m_2}.$$

Also, assume that $n_1 < n_2$, so $m_1 < m_2$. Thus, for $m_1 \geq 5$ we have

$$|n_i \log \delta - \log(2C_\alpha) - (m_i + 2) \log \alpha| < \frac{6}{\alpha^{m_i}} \tag{12}$$

for both $i = 1, 2$. Then we multiply the inequality (12) for $i = 1$ with n_2 and for $i = 2$ with n_1 , subtract them and apply the triangle inequality to get that

$$\begin{aligned} & |(n_2 - n_1) \log(2C_\alpha) + (n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2)) \log \alpha| \\ &= |n_2(n_1 \log \delta - \log(2C_\alpha) - (m_1 + 2) \log \alpha) \\ &\quad - n_1(n_2 \log \delta - \log(2C_\alpha) - (m_2 + 2) \log \alpha)| \\ &\leq n_2 |n_1 \log \delta - \log(2C_\alpha) - (m_1 + 2) \log \alpha| \\ &\quad + n_1 |n_2 \log \delta - \log(2C_\alpha) - (m_2 + 2) \log \alpha| \\ &\leq \frac{6n_2}{\alpha^{m_1}} + \frac{6n_1}{\alpha^{m_2}} < \frac{12n_2}{\alpha^{m_1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Now, we are ready to apply Theorem 3 with

$$\eta_1 = 2C_\alpha, \eta_2 = \alpha, \quad b_1 = n_2 - n_1, \quad b_2 = n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2).$$

Observe that $n_2 - n_1 < n_2$. Thus, we have

$$|n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2)| \leq (n_2 - n_1) \frac{\log(2C_\alpha)}{\log \alpha} + \frac{12n_2}{\alpha^{m_1} \log \alpha} < 2.5n_2.$$

Since $\mathbb{L} = \mathbb{Q}(\alpha) = 3$, we can take

$$\log B_1 = \max \left\{ h(\eta_1), \frac{|\log \eta_1|}{3}, \frac{1}{3} \right\} = h(2C_\alpha)$$

and

$$\log B_2 = \max \left\{ h(\eta_2), \frac{|\log \eta_2|}{3}, \frac{1}{3} \right\} = \frac{1}{3}.$$

Thus,

$$b' = \frac{|(n_2 - n_1)|}{3 \cdot \frac{1}{3}} + \frac{n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2)}{3 \cdot 1.84} < 2n_2.$$

We put

$$\Lambda := (n_2 - n_1) \log 2C_\alpha + (n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2)) \log \alpha.$$

By virtue of Theorem 3, we get

$$\log |\Lambda| > -24.34 \cdot 3^4 (\max\{\log 2n_2 + 0.14, 7, 0.5\})^2 (1.84)(1/3),$$

which further implies

$$\log |\Lambda| > -1210 (\max\{\log 2n_2 + 0.14, 7, 0.5\})^2.$$

Combining this with (13), we get

$$m_1 \log \alpha - \log(12n_2) < 1210 (\max\{\log 2n_2 + 0.14, 7, 0.5\})^2. \tag{14}$$

If $\log 2n_2 + 0.14 < 7$, then $n_2 < 473$. Then (14) gives

$$m_1 \log \alpha < \log(12 \cdot 473) + 1210 \cdot 7^2.$$

Thus, $m_1 < 59300$. Hence, $n_1 < n_2 < 473$ and $m_1 < 59300$ in this case. If $n_2 \geq 473$, then

$$m_1 \log \alpha < \log(12n_2) + 1210 (\log 2n_2 + 0.14)^2,$$

which implies

$$m_1 < 2.62 \log(12n_2) + 3165.6 (\log 2n_2 + 0.14)^2. \tag{15}$$

Since $\alpha^{m_1+1} > \delta^{n_1} \geq \delta$, we get

$$\log \delta < m_1 \log \alpha + \log \alpha < 1.1 \log(12n_2) + 1210.1 (\log 2n_2 + 0.14)^2 + \log \alpha.$$

Combining the above inequality with (10) and since $n_2 < m_2 + 2$, we have

$$m_2 < 24.33 \cdot 10^{13} (1 + \log(m_2 + 2)) [1.1 \log(12(m_2 + 2)) + 1210.1 (\log 2(m_2 + 2) + 0.14)^2 + \log \alpha],$$

which gives

$$m_2 < 4.4 \cdot 10^{22}. \tag{16}$$

Using (16) in (11) gives

$$n_2 < 5 \cdot 10^{15}, \tag{17}$$

which together with (15) gives

$$m_1 < 4.33 \cdot 10^6.$$

This was when $m_1 \geq 5$. But, if $m_1 < 5$, then from inequality (6), we have

$$\frac{\delta^{n_1}}{\alpha^2} < X_{n_1} = N_{m_1} \leq \alpha^{m_1-1}.$$

Thus, $n_1 \log \delta < (m_1 + 1) \log \alpha$, which gives $n_1 < 3$. Since $\delta \leq \alpha^{m_1+1} \leq \alpha^5 < 7$, it follows from (10) that

$$m_2 < 24.33 \cdot 10^{13}(\log 7)(1 + \log(m_2 + 2)),$$

which implies

$$m_2 < 1.9 \cdot 10^{16}.$$

Using the above inequality in (11), we obtain that

$$n_2 < 3.7 \cdot 10^{15}.$$

Comparing these bounds with (16) and (17), obtained in the case $m \geq 5$, we conclude that (16) and (17) hold for all $m \geq 1$. Now, we summarize what we have proved so far.

Lemma 3. *All solutions to $x_{n_i} = N_{m_i}$ for $i = 1, 2$ with $1 \leq m_1 < m_2$ and $n_1 < n_2$ satisfy*

$$m_1 < 4.33 \cdot 10^6, m_2 < 4.4 \cdot 10^{22} \quad \text{and} \quad n_2 < 5 \cdot 10^{15}.$$

To reduce the bounds obtained above we use continued fractions and the Baker-Davenport reduction method. Put $\chi := -\frac{\log 2C\alpha}{\log \alpha}$. Assume $m_1 > 230$. Inequality (13) implies

$$|(n_2 - n_1)\chi - (n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2))| < \frac{12n_2}{\alpha^{m_1} \log \alpha}.$$

Using Lemma 3, we have

$$\frac{24}{\log \alpha}(n_2 - n_1)n_2 < 63(n_2 - n_1)n_2 < 63n_2^2 < 1.6 \cdot 10^{33} < \alpha^{m_1},$$

which leads to

$$\frac{12n_2}{\alpha^{m_1} \log \alpha} < \frac{1}{2(n_2 - n_1)}.$$

Thus, we get

$$\left| \chi - \frac{n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2)}{n_2 - n_1} \right| < \frac{12n_2}{(n_2 - n_1)\alpha^{m_1} \log \alpha}.$$

So, $\frac{n_2(m_1+2)-n_1(m_2+2)}{n_2-n_1}$ is a convergent of $-\frac{\log 2C_\alpha}{\log \alpha}$. Obviously $(n_2 - n_1) < n_2 < 5 \cdot 10^{15}$. Let $[a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots] = [2, 2, 8, 1, 8, 1, 1, 4, 1, 2, 1, 3, 2, 1, 16, 23, 5, 1, 1, 1, 1, 13, \dots]$ be the continued fraction expansion of χ . Let p_k/q_k be the k th convergent. We recall an estimate (see [13, Theorem 163]) that

$$\frac{1}{(a_k + 2)q_k^2} < \left| \chi - \frac{p_k}{q_k} \right|,$$

where a_{k+1} is the $(k + 1)$ th partial quotient of χ defined as above. Using *Mathematica*, we find that

$$q_{37} < 5 \cdot 10^{15} < q_{38}.$$

Further, the maximum of $a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, 38)$ is $23 = a_{15}$. Thus, we have

$$\frac{1}{25(n_2 - n_1)^2} < \left| \chi - \frac{n_2(m_1 + 2) - n_1(m_2 + 2)}{n_2 - n_1} \right| < \frac{12n_2}{(n_2 - n_1)\alpha^{m_1} \log \alpha},$$

which implies

$$\alpha^{m_1} \log \alpha < (12n_2) \cdot (25(n_2 - n_1)) < 300n_2^2 < 7.5 \cdot 10^{33}, \text{ by Lemma 3.}$$

Thus, we get $m_1 < 207$. Since we assumed $m_1 > 230$ it follows in fact that $m_1 \leq 230$. Then (6) gives $n_1 < 91$. These upper bounds (on n_1 and m_1) make it possible to compute all n_1 and m_1 . Define

$$P_n^+(x) = \frac{(x + \sqrt{x^2 - 1})^n + (x - \sqrt{x^2 - 1})^n}{2}$$

and

$$P_n^-(x) = \frac{(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1})^n + (x - \sqrt{x^2 + 1})^n}{2}.$$

We use the fact that $x_n = P_n^\epsilon(x_1)$ for $\epsilon \in \pm 1$. All the d s can be calculated from $x_1^2 - \epsilon = dy_1^2$ for some integers d and y_1 with d square free. Using *Mathematica* on the equations

$$P_{n_1}^+(x_1) = N_{m_1} \text{ and } P_{n_1}^-(x_1) = N_{m_1},$$

with $1 \leq m_1 \leq 230$ and $1 \leq n_1 < 91$, where $n_1 \leq m_1$ we get that, besides the trivial case $n_1 = 1$ (for both equations), which implies $x_1 = N_{m_1}$, $(n_1, m_1, x_1) = \{(2, 8, 2), (2, 10, 3), (2, 15, 8)\}$ are the only solutions in -1 case. Now, applying (12) and Lemma 1, we verify the following new solutions to Equation (4). Observe that

$$\left| n_2 \frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha} - (m_2 + 2) + \chi \right| < 16 \cdot \alpha^{-m_2}.$$

Put $\delta_1 = 2 + \sqrt{5}$, $\delta_2 = 3 + \sqrt{10}$ and $\delta_3 = 8 + \sqrt{65}$. The convergents of the continued fraction expansions of $\frac{\log \delta_i}{\log \alpha}$, ($i = 1, 2, 3$) whose denominator exceeds $6 \cdot 5 \cdot 10^{15}$ and corresponding ϵ_i are positive, are

$$\begin{aligned} q_{1,31} &= 61214844407183281 \\ q_{2,32} &= 282910657514169795 \quad \text{and} \\ q_{3,37} &= 61968676817803112 \end{aligned}$$

for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively. Note that $\frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha}$ is transcendental by Gelfond-Schneider Theorem [2, Theorem 2.1] and hence irrational. Now, we apply Lemma 1 with $u = n_2, v = m_2 + 2, \tau = \frac{\log \delta}{\log \alpha}$ and $\mu = -\frac{\log 2C_\alpha}{\log \alpha}$. Further, corresponding to the three cases $q = q_{1,31}, q = q_{2,32}$, and $q = q_{3,37}$, we get $\epsilon_1 > 0.2794, \epsilon_2 > 0.0670$ and $\epsilon_3 > 0.2528$. Consequently, $m_2 \leq 111, n_2 \leq 48$ in the first case, $m_2 \leq 119, n_2 \leq 52$ in the second case and $m_2 \leq 118, n_2 \leq 51$ in the third case. However, we assumed $m_2 > 230$, which is a contradiction. So, $m_2 \leq 230$. With the help of *Mathematica*, we find no values of d that lead to atleast two positive integer solutions to Equation (4) except for $d = 2$ and hence proved.

It can be easily verified that the solutions to the Diophantine Equation (4) for $d = 2$ are in the form $(n, m) = (1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (5, 12)$.

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